

Synthetic and biocidal studies on oxovanadium complexes of substituted 2-pyrazolines having thienyl moiety

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Abstract : The oxovanadium(IV) complexes of 1-acetyl-3-aryl-5-(2-thienyl)pyrazolines have been synthesized. The structure of the isolated complexes have been elucidated on the basis of elemental analysis, molecular weight determination, molar conductance, magnetic moment and spectral (ESR, IR and UV) data. The ligands behaved as bidentate coordinating through carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. The ligands exhibited significant *in vitro* microbiocidal activity against phytopathogenic fungi viz. *Alternaria alternata*, *Collectotrichum capsicum*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Rhizoctonia solani* and bacteria viz. *Bacillus subtilis* and *E. coli* which was enhanced on metalation.

Keywords : Oxovanadium, pyrazoline, microbiocidal.

Introduction

Substituted pyrazolines, pyrazoles and pyrazolones have been acclaimed for their potential biocidal activities¹⁻³. Pyrazolines have been found to be useful in diverse applications in pharmaceutical and agrochemical industries⁴⁻⁶. Various substituents at different positions have marked effect on the biological activity of the ligands^{7,8}. The thienyl group itself is a highly potential biological active moiety. Further, the biological activities of the ligands often alter on coordination with suitable metal ions^{9,10}. Therefore, in the present study we have synthesized some sulphur containing pyrazolines with various substituents and their oxovanadium complexes and examined the biological effects of chelation against phytopathogenic fungi and bacteria. The choice of oxovanadium is based on the fact that it is an essential trace element in plants and animals^{11,12}. Vanadium containing complexes have extensively been reported for their antimicrobial activities^{13,14}.

Experimental

Materials and measurements :

2-Carboxyaldehyde thiophene and 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone were procured from Aldrich. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade and solvents were distilled

prior to use. IR spectra in Nujol mulls on KBr plates were obtained using a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on Hitachi 330 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra in CDCl₃ were recorded on a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) instrument using TMS as internal standard. ESR spectra of the complexes were recorded at room temperature (25 °C) and at liquid nitrogen temperature on a Varian E-line X-band spectrometer operating at 9.57 GHz using 100 KHz field modulation. Spectra of powdered samples and DMF solutions of the complexes were recorded in quartz tubes. The magnetic field calibration was checked using TCNE ($g = 2.00277$) as a g marker. Conductance values were determined in dry DMSO or DMF at 10⁻³ M on a Digital conductivity meter NDC 732. Thermogravimetric analysis was done on TGS-2 Perkin-Elmer Thermal Analyzer. Molecular weight determinations were carried out cryoscopically in dry nitrobenzene. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured on a Sherwood magnetic susceptibility balance (accuracy $\pm 2\%$) and carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were performed on an automatic elemental analyzer Carlo Erba Strumentazioni model 1106. Vanadium was determined as V₂O₅ after igniting the complex in an electrical furnace.

Synthesis of ligands :

The ligands were prepared in two steps as follows :

Synthesis of 1-aryl-3-(2-thienyl)-2-propen-1-one (ATP) :

1-Hydroxyacetophenone/1-hydroxy-2-acetonaphthone/2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone (0.2 mol), 2-carboxyaldehyde thiophene (0.2 mol) and sodium hydroxide (0.4 mol) in methanol (40 ml) were stirred at 0–5 °C for 48–50 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and acidified with sulphuric acid. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from methanol to afford ATP in 60–70% yield. The purity of the synthesized product was checked by means of thin layer chromatography regularly and by the IR and NMR studies.

Synthesis of 1-acetyl-3-aryl-5-(2-thienyl)-2-pyrazolines (AATP) :

To a solution of ATP (0.1 mol) in acetic acid (50 ml) was added dropwise hydrazine hydrate in excess (25 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 20–25 h. The resulting solution was concentrated, cooled and poured over ice water. The separated solid was washed with water, crystallized from methanol and dried under reduced pressure. Yield 70–75%. The purity of the synthesized product was checked by means of thin layer chromatography regularly and by the IR and NMR studies.

Synthesis of metal complexes :

Vanadyl sulphate (2.17 g, 0.01 mol), dissolved in the minimum amount of water (5 ml), was added to the solution of the corresponding ligand (0.02 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) and refluxed for 3 h. The solid thus separated was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under vacuum.

Results and discussion*NMR spectra :*

Condensation of (1) and (2) in alkaline methanol resulted in the formation of substituted 3-aryl-1-(substituted thienyl)-2-propen-1-one (3) in good yields. Their ¹H NMR spectra (Table 1) showed doublets at 7.4 and 8.0 ppm due to olefinic protons which were assigned *trans* configuration on the basis of the coupling constant (16 Hz). Reaction of (3) with excess of hydrazine hydrate in acetic acid afforded the required ligands (HL_I-HL_{III}). In these ligands, *trans* C₄-H was observed at upfield (2.52–2.85 ppm) as compared to its *cis* analog (3.27–3.56 ppm). Further, *J*_{4,5} *trans* was found to be smaller in magnitude (4–6) in comparison to *J*_{4,5} *cis* (12 Hz) and was in agreement with the reported literature values¹⁵. The integrated proton ratio of various groups, as evidenced from the spectrum of each ligand confirmed the proposed structure (Scheme 1).

All the metal complexes obtained were coloured (green-

Table 1. Analytical and ¹H NMR spectral data of 1-acetyl-3-aryl-5-(2-thienyl)-2-pyrazolines

Compound	M.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Analytical data (%) : Found (Calcd.)			¹ H NMR
			C	H	N	
HL _I	150	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	62.5 (62.9)	4.5 (4.9)	9.3 (9.8)	2.20 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.33–3.63 (1H, dd, C ₄ -H <i>trans</i>), 3.86–4.26 (1H, dd, C ₄ -H <i>cis</i>), 5.86–6.09 (1H, dd, C ₅ -H), 6.83–7.59 (7H, m, Ar-H and thienyl H)
HL _{II}	128	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	67.4 (67.8)	4.9 (4.8)	8.7 (8.3)	2.08 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.34–3.73 (1H, dd, C ₄ -H <i>trans</i>), 3.83–4.26 (1H, dd, C ₄ -H <i>cis</i>), 5.80–6.03 (1H, dd, C ₅ -H), 6.83–7.69 (9H, m, Ar-H and thienyl H)
HL _{III}	130	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	67.9 (67.8)	4.3 (4.8)	8.1 (8.3)	2.10 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.36–3.75 (1H, dd, C ₄ -H <i>trans</i>), 3.83–4.26 (1H, dd, C ₄ -H <i>cis</i>), 5.80–6.03 (1H, dd, C ₅ -H), 6.83–7.69 (9H, m, Ar-H and thienyl H)

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Scheme 1

ish blue to greenish brown) and stable at atmospheric conditions. These were insoluble in most of the common organic solvents except in polar solvents such as DMSO or DMF. The low molar conductance values ($5\text{--}15 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) in dry DMSO or DMF indicated their non-electrolytic nature and presence of coordinated water. The analytical and magnetic data are given in Table 2.

IR spectra :

A hypsochromic shift in $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ mode from $1575\text{--}1600 \text{cm}^{-1}$ to $1560\text{--}1580 \text{cm}^{-1}$ and a bathochromic shift in $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ mode from $800\text{--}810 \text{cm}^{-1}$ to $820\text{--}825 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the IR spectra of metal complexes suggested the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in coordination. The O-H stretching vibrations of the ligands ($3350\text{--}3420 \text{cm}^{-1}$) disappeared in the IR spectra of metal complexes indicating the participation of deprotonated phenolic oxygen in

complexation. This was further supported by a positive shift ($15\text{--}28 \text{cm}^{-1}$) in the phenolic $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ mode. The carbonyl group stretching vibrations and thienyl ring stretching vibrations remained unaltered in the spectra of metal complexes indicating the non-participation of carbonyl oxygen and thienyl sulphur in coordination. The M-O and M-N stretching vibrations appearing at $490\text{--}500$ and $415\text{--}418 \text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively confirmed the bidentate nature of the ligands¹⁶. The characteristic $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ mode was observed in the region $960\text{--}980 \text{cm}^{-1}$. The presence of strong band in the region $850\text{--}860 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the IR spectra of metal complexes depicted the presence of coordinated water molecule which disappeared on dehydration and it was also confirmed by reports of Fujita *et al.*¹⁷. Further, the existence of coordinated water molecule was validated by thermal gravimetric analysis. The

Table 2. Analytical and magnetic data of oxovanadium(IV) complexes of 1-acetyl-3-aryl-5-(2-thienyl)-2-pyrazolines

Compound	Molecular formula	Yield (%)	Analytical data (%) : Obsd. (Calcd.)				$\mu_{\text{eff.}}$ (B.M.)
			C	H	N	Metal	
[VO(L _I) ₂ H ₂ O]	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂ V	65	55.2 (54.9)	4.9 (4.3)	7.2 (8.5)	7.3 (7.8)	1.78
[VO(L _{II}) ₂ H ₂ O]	C ₃₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂ V	60	60.2 (60.4)	4.9 (4.2)	7.8 (7.4)	7.5 (6.7)	1.80
[VO(L _{III}) ₂ H ₂ O]	C ₃₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂ V	65	62.3 (60.4)	4.9 (4.2)	7.1 (7.4)	6.0 (6.7)	1.82

complex showed a weight loss in the temperature range 180–220 °C corresponding to the removal of one water molecule.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra :

The observed effective magnetic moment values (1.78–1.82 B.M.) were in the normal range expected for spin only value of a d^1 system and consistent with the mononuclear distorted octahedral complexes of oxovanadium(IV). The electronic spectra of the complexes $[\text{VO}(\text{L}_\text{I})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]-[\text{VO}(\text{L}_\text{III})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ exhibited two absorption bands in the region 12000–12210 and 17050–17140 cm^{-1} pertaining to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{yz}$, d_{xz} and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transitions respectively. The observed magnetic and electronic features were characteristic of distorted octahedral stereochemistry for the oxovanadium(IV) complexes. The ligand field stabilization energy (81.37–81.79 kJ mol^{-1}) also confirmed the proposed stereochemistry.

ESR spectra :

In the X-band ESR spectra of powdered samples of oxovanadium(IV) complexes, one signal around 3420 was observed (Fig. 1). The ESR spectrum of $[\text{VO}(\text{L}_\text{II})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ in DMF solution exhibited a set of eight hyperfine lines

arising due to the interaction of the unpaired electron of oxovanadium(IV) acceptor centre, placed in a distorted octahedral environment with the unpaired electron occupying predominantly the b_2 level in ground state. The g_\parallel , g_\perp and g_{iso} values for the complexes (Table 3) were consistent with the reported values^{18,19}. Room temperature ESR spectra result g -average values but lower temperature ESR pattern show eight bands due to g_\parallel and g_\perp and anisotropy is clearly visible at liquid nitrogen temperature in frozen solution.

Investigation of antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial activity of the ligands and their vanadyl complexes was evaluated for *in vitro* growth inhibition against phytopathogenic fungi viz. *Colletotrichum capsicum* and *Rhizoctonia solani* and bacteria viz. Gram-positive *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli* using the

Table 3. The ESR parameters of vanadyl complexes in DMF solution at room temperature

Compound	g_\parallel	g_\perp	g_{iso}
$[\text{VO}(\text{L}_\text{I})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	1.962	1.992	1.981
$[\text{VO}(\text{L}_\text{II})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	1.966	1.994	1.984
$[\text{VO}(\text{L}_\text{III})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	1.970	1.992	1.983

Fig. 1. The electronic spin resonance spectrum of $[\text{VO}(\text{L}_\text{II})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ in DMF solution at room temperature.

Table 4. Microbiocidal data of 1-acetyl-3-aryl-5-(thienyl)-2-pyrazolines and their oxovanadium complexes

Compound	<i>A. alternata</i>	<i>C. capsicum</i>	<i>F. oxysporum</i>	<i>R. solani</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
HL _I	100	100	100	> 100	50	50
[VO(L _I) ₂ H ₂ O]	50	50	50	50	12.5	25
HL _{II}	50	50	100	100	50	50
[VO(L _{II}) ₂ H ₂ O]	12.5	25	25	12.5	25	12.5
HL _{III}	50	50	50	50	50	25
[VO(L _{III}) ₂ H ₂ O]	6.25	25	12.5	12.5	25	6.25

serial dilution technique²⁰. The stock solutions were prepared by dissolving the compounds in DMSO. Proper conditions (temperature, pH, necessary nutrients and growth media) were employed for the preparation of cultures of fungi and bacteria. The incubating period for fungi and bacteria was 72 h at 37 °C and 24 h at 28 °C, respectively. The conventional fungicide 2-(methoxycarbonyl)benzimidazole (bavistin) and bactericide Streptopencillin were used for assessing the activity of the compounds. All the tests were carried out in triplicate and the concordant value reported. A comparative study of the MIC (minimum inhibitory concentration) values (Table 4) showed that the ligand HL_I was active at more than 100 ppm against *Colletotrichum capsicum*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli* but its vanadyl complex exhibited growth inhibition at 100, 100, 12.5 and 100 ppm respectively. The ligands HL_I showed complete growth inhibition at 100 ppm against *Rhizoctonia solani* but their complexes were active at 6.25 and 3.12 ppm respectively against this organism. The ligands HL_{II} and HL_{III} were found to be active at 50 ppm against *E. coli* while activity of their vanadyl complexes varied between 50–12.5 ppm. One of the important finding was that ligand HL_{III} was more potent than ligand HL_{II} which in turn was more active than HL_I. This was due to their difference in the presence and orientation of benzene ring. A perusal of the antimicrobial activity data reveals that the activity of the ligands was enhanced on their chelation to the oxovanadium(IV) acceptor center. However, none of the compounds possessed better inhibitory action than the conventional fungicide and bactericide.

Higher activity of metal complexes may be due to the effect of metal ions on the normal cell process. Chelation increases the lipophilic character of the metal complexes which probably leads to breakdown of permeability bar-

rier of the cell wall resulting in interference with normal cell process²¹. The ligand HL_{II} was ineffective against R.S. at 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ whereas its complex was potent at 25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Similarly, all other ligands were found to be less effective than their metal complexes.

The complexes of 1-acetyl-3-aryl-5-(2-thienyl)-2-pyz (HL_I–HL_{III}) with oxovanadium(IV) proved to be potential microbiocidal agents. The complexes were more potent than the corresponding ligands.

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